

ESP2024 (November 2024)

Author: Lori Giagnacovo

Co-authors: Els Verachtert, Frederik Priem, Markus Sydenham, Tijana Nikolić Lugonja & Maja Arok

Title: Nature-based solutions through the use of Essential Biodiversity Variables in Land Dynamics predictions.

Target 8 and 11 of the GBF aim to restore, maintain and enhance ecosystem services and evaluate policy and management that minimize negative impacts and stimulate positive impacts on biodiversity. However, there are still substantial data gaps for reliable estimates in services provided by ecosystems to people and how positive climate action is incorporated by countries. To fill this gap, we need to evaluate essential ecosystem service variables (EESVs) and essential biodiversity variables (EBVs). The state of the biodiversity within an ecosystem is key in determining the ecosystem integrity and is therefore a very important indicator in assessing the capacity of an ecosystem to provide its potential ecosystem services. This is illustrated by the theory that a resilient and intact ecosystem will have a high level of functional redundancy in comparison to a degraded ecosystem. EBVs can be designed to focus on ecosystem structure or ecosystem functioning. In the OBSGESSION project, we will create data cubes composed by a large number of data (i.e. remote sensing data, in-situ data, citizen science, eDNA, etc.), from which an essential biodiversity variable (EBV) can be derived by a specific metric. Time series analyses of EBVs may point out where and when biodiversity is declining. As an example, EUNIS habitat maps can serve as ecosystem distribution EBV. We plan to use this EBV in the SONATA project for Serbia. There we will evaluate alternative land use scenarios to spatially optimize nature based solutions (NbS) in the area. This way, we aim to gain insights in how, where and which NbS can best be implemented in targeting conservation and/or restoration of biodiversity and ecosystem services.

- ➔ *Emphasis on Global Biodiversity Framework, ecosystem services, Nature-based Solutions. Using habitat maps as an ecosystem structure EBV and link it to scenario analyses in the context of Nature-based solutions planning.*